

A Swarm Control by Distributed Attractant and Repellent, and its Application for a Stage Effect in Contemporary Ballet

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Abstract

It is a well known phenomenon that the collective behaviour of ants is achieved through the diffusion of pheromones secreted by individuals. The authors applied this mechanism to interactive visual stage effects for a contemporary ballet choreographed by Jiří Kylián at the Netherlands Dance Theatre in 2008. The dance performance entitled “Gods and Dogs” has been performed in various European dance companies. In 2023, the software underwent a complete revision to adapt to the latest computing and peripheral equipment. By utilising the division of tasks between multi-core CPUs and GPUs, the software can now respond with shorter latency and generate visual output at higher frame rates in high resolution. Parameter tuning is also crucial in matching the visuals to the designer’s preferences. The experimental results regarding the tendency and sensitivity of certain parameters for diffusion, as well as the balance factor between attraction and repulsion, can aid the design process.

Introduction

The phenomena that collective behaviour of ants is due to the diffusion of pheromones secreted by individuals is widely known in both ethology (Wilson, 1963) and complex systems (Dorigo et al., 1999; Gazi and Passino, 2003). It is also known that the secretion and diffusion of species-specific attractants and repellents and their detection assist coordination and avoidance behaviours among individuals, whether of the same or different species (Dicke and Sabelis, 1988). Some researchers in the field of swarm robotics have pursued hardware designs inspired from this mechanism, typically for collective behaviour in navigation tasks (Arvin et al., 2015). Not only for science or engineering, such complex phenomena have also been applied to produce artistic expressions (Greenfield and Machado, 2015). In 2008, the authors created an interactive artwork based on a computer simulation of this mechanism (Bisig and Unemi, 2010) and, in parallel, applied it to the interactive visual stage effects for contemporary ballet (Bisig and Unemi, 2009).

These stage effects were used in the final scene of “Gods and Dogs”, a piece choreographed and directed by Jiří Kylián and performed by the Netherlands Dance Theatre, a contemporary ballet company based in The Hague, the Netherlands

(Kylián, 2008a). It was subsequently performed again in the Netherlands and other parts of Europe, including Oslo, Zurich, Lyon, Monte Carlo, Madrid, Munich, Dresden, London and Prague. On the occasion of the re-performance of the piece at the Palais Garnier by the Paris Opera Ballet in December 2023, the software was completely revised to adapt to the latest computing and peripheral equipment. By utilising the division of tasks among multi-core CPUs and GPUs, more detailed visuals and rapid interactive responses are now possible.

The following sections describe the stage effect, the computational model using diffusion and evaporation of virtual attractants and repellents, the experimental analysis of the tendency and sensitivity of the effects to parameter settings, and the algorithms for simulating the swarm and the speed-up gained by parallel computation.

Projecting the swarm onto the dancer’s body

Lighting plays an important role, along with various tools for stage scenography and decoration in performing arts such as theatre play, dance, instrumental music and singing. In recent years, with the development of video equipment, the effects have been diversified by projecting images onto the stage using projectors and lasers, in combination with light sources with different colours, directions and diffusion. Furthermore, the application of image processing and sensor technology has made it possible to create visual effects that respond to the movements of the performers on stage.

Brief history of the collaboration

In 2008, the authors have been working together on the piece “Vanishing Twin” by Jiří Kylián (Kylián, 2008b), which was premiered in February 2008. They co-created a stage background image that responds to the dancers’ movements by applying a simulation of collective behaviour based on the BODIS system (Reynolds, 1987). Afterwards, they developed a technique for projecting a visualisation of swarms onto the visitor’s body and showed Jiří Kylián an experimental video, which he decided to apply in his next ballet piece. Images of lines looking like worms swarming over the body

Figure 1: Still images from a video recording of the performance “Gods and Dogs”. Dancer: Idan Sharabi. © Netherlands Dance Theater II, 2008. A swarm is roaming on his body.

were projected in response to the movements of the solo male dancer on his body in the final scene of the piece. Figure 1 shows still images from a video recording of the original performance.

Basic technique

The system extracts the partial area that is the projection target from the image captured by a video camera and controls the collective behaviour of the swarm so that it gathers in the relevant area.

One of the essential technical issues to be solved is to ensure that the projected image does not affect the image processing for extracting the target area. The light emitted from a projector is usually limited to the visible light band and contains few components of infrared or ultraviolet light (Seime and Hardeberg, 2002). Exploiting this property, near-infrared light, which cannot be seen by the human eye but can be captured by video cameras is used to illuminate the stage. Fortunately, the light emitted from incandescent light bulbs, which are still widely used in theatres, contains wavelength components corresponding to near-infrared rays. It is of sufficient intensity to be used as near-infrared light source even when the visible light bands are blocked using filters.

CCD and CMOS sensors, which are widely used as image sensors in digital cameras, are also sensitive to near-infrared radiation (Davidson, 2016). For conventional applications, a filter that blocks near-infrared rays is attached so that only visible light is captured. By replacing this filter with one that blocks visible light rays and transmits near-infrared rays, the camera can be used to detect near-infrared light. Many webcams widely used for attaching to personal computers don't provide the possibility to replace such filters, but many industrial cameras offer such flexibility, and the equipment described above can be assembled relatively easily by combining commercially available products.

The information flow of image data from camera input to projector output is shown in Figure 2 where “Tracker” is the application software for image processing and “DT5mC” is

Figure 2: Information flow among hardware and software components.

the application software for swarm simulation and video image generation. The extraction of the target area by image processing was developed mainly using the openFrameworks library. The target area is sent as bitmap to the application software for video generation. In this paper, the image processing part is omitted and the video image generation is described.

In 2008, most cameras in general use had a resolution of 640×480 and a frame rate of 30 fps, video projectors had a higher resolution such as 1024×768 and the same frame rate, and the performance of computer CPUs was about 2.8 to 3.2 GHz clock frequency, with 4 cores and no super-threading even in high-performance versions such as the ones used in Mac Pro (Wikipedia, 2023). Compared with the resolution of 1920×1080 and frame rate of 60 fps that have become standard in recent years, the amount of data requiring processing is $1/13.5$, but the calculation speed is the rate-limiting factor, and the calculation can barely keep up with the frame rate by using parallel processing with multi-threading.

Theatre-specific setup

Figure 3 illustrates the installation of the equipment in the Palais Garnier. Designed by Charles Garnier and built between 1861 and 1875, it has a domed ceiling with a large chandelier hanging from it and four layers of balcony surrounding the sides in the style of a traditional European opera house. It seats approximately 2,000 people and is one of Europe's leading opera houses along with Vienna, Milan, Munich and so on (Kaldor, 2002).

Figure 3: Setups in Palais Garnier, Paris.

The camera, projector and near-infrared light are installed on the ceiling of the third level balcony and are connected to an operator console in the backstage area by a high-speed wired LAN, enabling remote control mainly using the OSC protocol (Wright and Freed, 1997). The computer for generating the stage effects presented here was installed on the third level balcony, close to the camera. This computer was operated from the operator console via screen sharing using VNC. Figure 4 shows the control window displayed on the screen.

In many theatres of modern design, a camera and other equipment can be installed on a bridge near the ceiling. In this case, standard lenses can be used, although keystone correction is required to correct the shape of the projection area. In the setup in the Palais Garnier, the width of the stage on which the dancers move around is about 15 m, and the distance from the camera to the stage is about 30 m. Both the camera and the projector are equipped with telephoto lenses. To cope with the difficulty of adjusting the projection position and size by physically manipulating the lens and installation position, the graphical user interface shown in the upper part of Figure 4 provides additional controls.

Virtual chemical placement, diffusion and evaporation

This section describes the computational simulation of the placement, diffusion and evaporation of virtual chemicals in two-dimensional space.

Figure 4: Control window of DT5mC for parameter settings and controls.

Figure 5: Approximation of virtual chemical density.

Representation of distribution

Although it would be ideal if the distribution could be precisely expressed in a continuous space, here we use a discrete space divided by a square lattice due to limitations in the handling of data on digital computers. The density of the substance at a position specified by continuous coordinates values is approximately calculated. As shown in Figure 5, the density $V(\mathbf{p})$ at the position \mathbf{p} is calculated from the value recorded on the lattice element containing the position \mathbf{p} and three adjacent elements close to \mathbf{p} . The following formula is used to obtain the weighted sum among four values, M_1, M_2, M_3 and M_4 , in these lattice elements as interpolated value, that is,

$$V(\mathbf{p}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^4 w_i M_i}{\sum_{i=1}^4 w_i}. \quad (1)$$

The weight w_i is calculated using the distance d_i between the position \mathbf{p} and the centre point of each element, where $w_i = 1$ when $d_i = 0$, $w_i = 0$ when $d_i \geq 1$, and monotonically decreasing with $d_i \in [0, 1]$ using the following formula.

$$w_i = (\cos(\min(1, d_i)\pi) + 1)/2 \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{p} and d_i are scaled so that the spacing between adjacent elements is 1.

Arrangement of attractants

Each individual in the swarm moves in the direction along the density gradient of the attractant. In this application, the attractants are placed in the target area obtained by processing the camera image. The information on the target area is in the form of a bitmap, i.e. a two-dimensional bit array representing the entire image area. The bits corresponding to the target area are set to 1 and the others to 0. The resolution of the camera image is 1920×1080 , but to reduce the amount of communication with the image processing application and the amount of computation during image generation, the image size is scaled to a 640×360 bitmap. A grid of the same size is constructed as an array of 32 bits floating point numbers to represent the distribution of virtual chemical substances. The values of lattice elements corresponding to bit values of 1 are set to the maximum value ($=1.0$) for each step.

Figure 6: Three types of representation of repellent placement. \mathbf{p} indicates the position of individual. The greyscale paint represents the amount of repellent placed. The darkest grey corresponds to the maximum value 1.0.

Arrangement of repellents

In principle, a swarm is composed of a set of individuals that follow the same action rules. According to this principle, all individuals are summoned to the attractant, and individuals are concentrated in the area as result. It is desirable for the visual effect to have an even distribution of individuals without excessive crowding in the target area where the density of the attractant is high. To achieve this, each individual secretes a repellent substance to avoid being in close proximity to each other. However, as the coordinates of the individuals take continuous values, the position of the substances in the environment cannot be accurately represented by a discrete grid. As in the approximate calculation of the density distribution described above, a weighted allocation to the neighbouring elements according to the position of the individuals could be used. But here, for simplicity, the system simply changes the density of one element containing the individual position to a constant value ($=1.0$). Figure 6 illustrates these three types of representation methods.

Diffusion and evaporation

Attractants and repellents independently change their density distribution over time by diffusion and evaporation, respectively. Diffusion is achieved by taking the average of the values of neighbouring elements for each element, similar to the blurring filter in image processing. Here, to simplify the calculation, the average value of the values in a square region with constant side length K is calculated in which the target element is at its centre. To implement evaporation, multiplication is applied by a factor E ($0 < E \leq 1$) representing the evaporation rate. The formula for obtaining the density $M'(i, j)$ of the next step from the current density $M(i, j)$ of the element (i, j) is as follows.

$$M'(i, j) = \frac{E}{K^2} \sum_{g=-k}^k \sum_{h=-k}^k M(i+g, j+h), \quad k = \lfloor K/2 \rfloor \quad (3)$$

where K is assumed to be an odd number.

Swarm simulation

A swarm consists of a number of individuals that move according to the same action rules. Each individual possesses a position, orientation and elapsed time as its state. It moves in the simulation space of the size 640×360 .

Initial state

Each individual is initially placed at an arbitrary position on the top, bottom, left and right boundaries of the simulation space using a uniform random number. The orientation is set to face the centre of the simulation space to ensure that it remains within the simulation space during the early steps even if the virtual chemicals are not yet placed anywhere in the space. The elapsed time is assigned a uniform random number whose maximum value is the lifespan given as a parameter. The lattice grids for chemicals are initially empty, that is, all of the element values are zero, but at the first step of the simulation, the detection of the target area provides attractants and the individuals secrete repellents.

Basic Movement

Each individual determines its next location at each simulation step using the following calculation process. An individual moves towards the direction with the higher density of the attractant and towards the direction with the lower density of the repellent. At the same time some randomness is added so that the movement appears more lifelike. The individual moves relatively slowly within the target area with a high density of the attractant substance and rapidly in other areas, so that it quickly follows the movement and deformation of the target area.

The elapsed time is updated at each step, and individuals that have reached the end of their lifespan are forced to move to an arbitrary position within the simulation space, with the remaining life span set to the maximum value. Since the destination of individuals that have reached the end of their lifetime is often outside the target area, if the target area moves fast, these fast-searching individuals take on the role of searching the target area they have moved to.

Movement speed

The travel distance for each time step is determined using the standard speed ratio R_S , maximum speed ratio R_H , low speed threshold V_{slow} and high speed threshold V_{rapid} given as parameters. The step length l' is determined by the basic distance multiplied by a uniform random number in the range from 0.3 to 1.5. If the current density of the attractant $V_A(\mathbf{p})$ is denser than V_{slow} , the factor is R_S . If the density is less than V_{rapid} , it is R_H . If the density is less than V_{slow} and denser than V_{rapid} , the distance is multiplied by a linearly interpolated value between R_S and R_H . The equation to calculate the actual step length l' is expressed as follows.

$$l' = \begin{cases} l \cdot R_S & V_A(\mathbf{p}) > V_{slow} \\ l \cdot R_H & V_A(\mathbf{p}) < V_{rapid} \\ l \cdot \left(\frac{V_A(\mathbf{p}) - V_{rapid}}{V_{slow} - V_{rapid}} (R_H - R_S) + R_S \right) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Movement direction

The direction of movement is determined using the average rotation angle, the number of search points n and the avoidance coefficient α given as parameters. The maximum rotation angle ϕ is determined by the standard rotation angle multiplied by a uniform random number in the range from 0.5 to 1.5. Let θ be the angle representing the current orientation of the individual, the candidate orientations $\{\theta_j \mid j = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ to be taken are organised by evenly dividing the interval $[\theta - \phi, \theta + \phi]$. For each θ_j , the position \mathbf{q}_j is calculated as the candidate position after moving from the current location in the direction of that angle by the previously calculated step length l . The densities of the attractant $V_A(\mathbf{q}_j)$ and of the repellent $V_R(\mathbf{q}_j)$ are determined using the formula 1. Then the weighted difference between these two densities is calculated using α . The angle corresponding to the maximum of these values is selected and the orientation θ' in the next step is determined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} k &= \arg \max_j (1 - \alpha)V_A(\mathbf{q}_j) - \alpha V_R(\mathbf{q}_j) \\ \theta' &= \theta_k, \quad \theta_j = \theta + 2\phi([\frac{n}{2}] - j)/(n - 1) \\ \mathbf{q}_j &= \mathbf{p}_t + (l' \cos \theta_j, l' \sin \theta_j). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

If there are multiple angles with the same maximum value, one of them is selected at random. Figure 7 shows an example of a candidate set of destination positions when the number of search points n is 5.

Figure 7: Shape and movement of an individual worm.

Figure 8: Sample distribution of virtual chemicals and a swarm image.

Drawing the swarm

To make the individuals look like caterpillars or worms, they are drawn as line segments connecting the previous positions of the last few steps, as shown in Figure 7. The thickness and length are specified by the parameters. The number of previous positions taken into account depends on the maximum distance threshold from the current position, and the last line segment is drawn up to the halfway position so that it becomes the length of the remaining portion.

The colour of each joint between the line segments is determined including the opacity according to the density of the attractant at the position. Each line segment is rendered using two opacity values for its beginning and ending points with a linear gradient. If the density is high, the colour is opaque, and if the density is close to zero, the colour is transparent, so that only the individuals in the target area are visible.

Figure 8 shows examples of images of attractants, repellents and worms. The image of the swarm on the right side of the figure has been inverted for printing purposes, and the actual projected image appears to be darker in the surroundings with white worms swarming on the surface of the dancer’s body.

Parameter tuning on repellents

As previously mentioned, this system requires the adjustment of several parameters to ensure that the visual effects match the designer’s aesthetic preference. These parameters include length, thickness, speed, turning angle, and colour, all of which are crucial to the appearance of the swarm. Additionally, the parameters for virtual chemicals play a significant role in the swarm’s behaviour. To investigate the effects of the diffusion window size K in equation 3 applied to repellents and the factor of avoidance α in equation 5 on the density of individuals in the simulation space, we employed the following three indices as measurements of density distribution.

The first index is the percentage of visible individuals in the swarm. An individual worm is visible when its position

is inside the target area and does not appear in the projected image when it is located outside. Instead, it is moving fast to scout the target in order to adapt to its movement and deformation. This role alternation is useful when the target is moving fast, however it is inefficient from a computational point of view because a large swarm would be required to have a sufficient number of visible individuals while many others are scouting around.

It is preferable that the individuals in the target area are distributed as uniformly as possible. The combination of effects from attractants and repellents may cause a difference in densities between the border and centre of the target area. If repellents have no effect ($\alpha = 0$), individuals tend to concentrate in the centre, resulting in an almost empty border area. The second and third indices relate to the uniformity of the distribution of visible individuals. To measure this feature, the number of neighbours in relatively close proximity to each visible individual is counted. The average and standard deviation of these numbers are then calculated. Smaller values for both indices suggest a more uniform distribution. To account for variations in the number of individuals, the maximum distance D_c to determine whether a neighbour is considered “close” should be appropriately calculated and used to normalise the index values. Here, the square root of the area size per individual within the target area is used as the limit.

To conduct an experimental simulation of swarm behaviour, we prepared a still image similar to the shape shown in the left image of Figure 8 as a target area. The number of individuals is set to the relatively large number of 1,000, which makes the counts more stable. The simulation runs were examined for each combination of alternative values of K and α . After skipping the early 600 steps from the initial state, index values are summed up in the next 600 steps, in order not to include the transition phase from the initial state before reaching the stable distribution. Figure 9 shows the average values across 600 steps of these three indices. In the right figure, the values divided by the average are plotted

Figure 9: Indices for density distribution of swarm for alternative values of α and K .

instead of the raw values of standard deviation for intuitive understanding.

As shown in the left figure, if either α or K is smaller, the number of visible individuals is larger. However, the index values are insensitive to α in the range from 0.1 to 0.5 when K is smaller than 7. Therefore, it is helpful to set to the range from 11 to 15 to keep the flexibility of adjusting α , though a larger value of K increases the computation cost. Concerning the distribution uniformity, smaller values of the average number of near neighbours are found when $(K, \alpha) = (7, 0.3)$, $(5, 0.5)$ and $(7, 0.5)$ as shown in the middle figure. This index value becomes larger when α is approaching to 1, because the individual distribution in the target area is sparse, and the proximity threshold D_c is long, then a high percentage of individuals within the target area is recognised as near neighbours. On the standard deviation ratio, they are in the cases of $(9, 0.6)$, $(11, 0.5)$ and $(9, 0.3)$. It is difficult to determine which parameter combination is best, but the above results suggest $K \in [7, 11]$ and $\alpha \in [0.3, 0.6]$ are appropriate ranges for a designer's choice.

Figure 10 shows sample images of a swarm alternating the value of α when $K = 11$ and $N = 300$. It is clear that the swarm concentrates in the centre area when $\alpha = 0$ as described above. In case of $\alpha = 0.2$, it is observed that some part of the dancer's arms is not covered by the swarm and the legs look thinner than the provided image. The larger α becomes, the more sparsely the visible individuals are distributed. It is clear that a small number of individuals appears when $\alpha = 1$ as the attractants have no effect. Based on a comparison among these images, it can be said that the value of α should be in the range between 0.5 to 0.7.

Faster computation by parallel processing

Calculations of the distribution of virtual chemical substances can be performed in parallel for each element, and the number of elements is relatively large ($640 \times 360 = 230,400$), so the authors used calculations on a GPU, which is suitable for applying the same operation to many data. A machine equipped with an Apple Silicon M2 chip and running macOS 13 was used to perform the calculations, and the soft-

ware was developed to perform parallel processing using the Metal Compute Shader.

The simulation of a swarm is calculated in parallel for each individual. In the case of BOIDS, the computation of interactions among individuals is necessary, which means that the computation time is proportional to the square of the number of individuals unless any measures are taken to suppress the computation cost. However, the number of calculations required for the method introduced here is proportional to the number of individuals. Even when placing repellent substances, as described above, the fixed maximum value is assigned to the corresponding element regardless of the current value. Therefore it is not necessary to manage the access control of the memory even when several individuals are placed on the same element in the same step. The result is not affected by the order of assignment. The software was developed assuming that the number of individuals constituting a swarm, i.e. the population size, would be at most several thousand, but in the actual performance, the number of individuals was set to 300 for aesthetic reasons concerning the density of individuals in the projection image. At this level of parallelism, the advantages of the GPU could not be utilised to a great extent. A CPU is superior for single-thread performance. The vector arithmetic operations in the single core and multi-threading functions among the cores are more helpful to accelerate the complicated calculations than in the case of the GPU.

The virtual chemical distribution information needs to be accessed by both the CPU and the GPU, but Apple Silicon's chip has a large enough memory that can be shared between the CPU and the GPU, so there is no load from data transfer that would be required when using an independent GPU board.

The GPU is also used for rendering, but with only a few hundred polylines and a few thousand vertices, the load is relatively small.

The above innovations have made it possible to achieve an acceptable performance for a resolution of 1920×1080 pixels at the frame rate in 60 fps. That is, a single step of the calculation from camera capture to image projection takes

Figure 10: Variations of swarm distribution for different values of α , when $K = 11$ and $N = 300$.

less than 1/60th of a second without recognisable delay for the stage performance.

Conclusion

The performances of four of Kylián’s pieces including “Gods and Dogs” by the Paris Opera Ballet from 8th to 31st December 2023 were successfully completed under the well-organised cooperation of all the staff. The stage effect described above worked effectively in collaboration with the video team of both the Kylian production and the Paris Opera.

We investigated the parameters’ sensitivity for the effects of repellents and presented the results above. These experiments are useful only for a still image but not a moving image for which other parameter settings are important to make the swarm respond better the dancer’s movement. The system is equipped with a number of parameters to be adjusted as shown in the control panel of Figure 4. Some of these parameters, particularly those related to attractants, should also be examined in a similar manner. Such analyses can provide useful insights for future applications of similar techniques in organising reactive swarms for various fields.

The capacity and speed of technical equipment has increased as a result of technological progress and dissemination, enabling more subtle and agile expression in works of art that use such equipment. Although a resolution of 1920×1080 pixels and the frame rate of 60 fps are supported here, cameras and projectors with 4K resolution (4096×2160 pixels and 3840×2160 pixels) are already available in the market even as consumer products, and it is expected that such high-resolution video data will be popularised soon in the theatre. It will be necessary to verify and improve the system to ensure sufficient performance when handling such high-resolution video data.

The implementation described above is possible thanks to a combination of several technologies that have improved in recent years. This includes not only the computing power of small computers, but also cameras, projectors, and the communication bandwidth between these devices. The graphical user interface facilitated by the operating system and the con-

venient software library also played an important role in facilitating the development process. When trying something innovative, one should always explore a wide variety of possibilities. The authors hope that this study will provide other developers with some inspiration to imagine how large an implementation is possible with recent technology.

In this performance, the choreography of the ballet is almost fixed, but improvisational variations by the dancers are allowed in the solo parts, and real-time response based on camera images is essential for the projected images to follow the movements of the dancers. However, the music used in the performance is not played live but pre-recorded, and the scene changes and main movements are performed in synchronisation with the music. Therefore the lighting effects and the start of the projection can be automatically executed each time by scheduling according to a prearranged time. In order to incorporate the operation of the computer into an environment integrated with the lighting control, an extension is needed to accept control by the OSC protocol. This time, the authors could not provide such a control interface function because they could not develop it in time, but they would like to extend it to support such automation if the opportunity arises next time.

The source code of the “DT5mC” software developed for video generation is available on GitHub <https://github.com/unemi/DT5mC>. The authors hope this code will be of interest to others.

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